

EXAMINATION MALPRACTICE: STRATEGIES, CAUSES AND SOLUTIONS IN SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN IWO LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, OSUN STATE

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Abstract

Examinations serve as a crucial tool for evaluating the objectives of teaching and learning in schools and assessing how well students have mastered the curriculum. However, students often resort to illicit means to pass exams, resulting in examination malpractices. This study investigates the causes, strategies, and solutions to examination malpractices in senior secondary schools within the Iwo Local Government area of Osun State. A total of 100 respondents, comprising both students and teachers, were randomly selected from two senior secondary schools in Iwo Local Government. Data were collected through a questionnaire and analysed using a descriptive survey method. The findings reveal that mobile phones are the most commonly used tools in malpractices, alongside traditional methods such as smuggling in materials, impersonation, and mass cheating. The causes of these malpractices include an excessive emphasis on academic certificates, limited spaces in tertiary institutions, inadequate teaching methods, and a lack of well-equipped libraries and laboratories. The consequences of these malpractices undermine the educational system, fostering irresponsibility, laziness, and corruption. Proposed solutions include stricter enforcement of laws, improved school facilities, enhanced teacher training, moral education, and effective implementation of continuous assessments.

Keywords: education, examination, malpractices, secondary school, teaching and learning

Introduction

The alarming rate of examination malpractices at all levels of the education sector poses a significant threat to the validity and reliability of any examination conducted in Nigeria. The recognition and value of certificates issued in the country seem diminishing over time. The blame has

been placed on moral decadence in society, and the high value placed on certificates for admission and employment were identified as some factors that also contribute to the high rate of examination malpractices. Education is pivotal for national development, influencing a nation's technological, sociological, and physical

progress (Shomoye et al., 2023). It is the process through which a person gains knowledge and enlightenment. It is a lifelong process that begins at birth and continues until death (Cooper & Olson, 2020; Tan, 2017). Education can be seen as the endeavour to shape or modify an individual's behaviour to equip them with desirable skills, habits, and attitudes to effectively contribute to the growth and development of the community in which they reside. During the educational process in a school, examination is considered the most important and often the only acceptable method of evaluating whether the objectives and goals of teaching and learning have been achieved. The examination serves as a key factor in gauging students' competence and progress, as highlighted by Nnam & Inah (2015) and supported by Ayoade & Farayola's (2020). Students are regularly tested to assess how well they have learned the curriculum, and their level of understanding is determined through examinations. This process serves as the basis for promotion from one class to another, and certificates are awarded upon achieving the required grades. In today's society, certificates hold significant importance, in contrast to the past when competency was judged primarily by experience and skill rather than formal qualifications.

Given the significance of education, students often resort to any means necessary to pass their exams, including illegal methods. They devise numerous ways to cheat, treating examinations as a do-or-die affair (Longat et al., 2021). Examination malpractices, however, lead to erroneous judgments, negatively impacting teachers, students, the education sector, and society at large (Ojonemi et al., 2013). Additionally, the country's reputation is tarnished abroad due to these issues. A key cause of examination malpractice is the excessive value placed on educational certificates, as they are often seen as

essential for securing good jobs. According to Onyibe (2015), moral decadence which is now rampant in society and the degree of value placed on personal achievement and certificates by most Nigerians have contributed immensely during this era to increase in examination malpractice and this has prompted parents to bribe their ways to assist their wards. Over-dependence on certificates as a yardstick to measure the knowledge and competence of individuals to be gainfully employed has led to a very high race by most people to have educational certificates (Odili, 2012). The rise in examination malpractices in Nigeria is largely due to insufficient capacity in tertiary institutions, creating intense competition among applicants. The pressure to achieve higher scores has led to an increase in malpractices, as only top scorers are likely to gain admission. Federal Ministry of Education (FME, 2016) reported that candidates admitted into universities ranged between 5% and 32% of the applicants for the period 1999 – 2016. In the 1999/2000 academic session a total of 417,773 candidates applied for admission while only 78,550 candidates were admitted, which shows an admission rate of 19%.

Maheshwari (2011) opined that various forms of malpractice are usually committed before the conduct stages, during the conduct stages, and evaluation stages of the examination. Ayanniyi & Anya (2017) stated that examination malpractices include giving examinations as a contract, assistance by lecturer or teacher, computerized means, impersonation, leakage of the examination paper, expo, tattooing of the body with likely answer, collusion among students, use of materials that are not acceptable during the examination, giraffe method and copying from answer booklet of others during the examination. In addition, Maheshwari (2011) also stated that forms of examination malpractices include

leakage of examination question papers, spying of answers from another candidate, exchange of answer booklet with another candidate, impersonation, misconduct that occurs during the examination, inappropriate conduct of invigilators/examiners, fake entries in examination registers, and issuing of fake certificates/degrees. Numerous solutions have been adopted by different examination bodies at the local, state and federal government levels and even by school stakeholders to curb the occurrence of examination malpractices. Some of the solutions are checking the examination cards of candidates sitting for the examination, forbidding the use of electronic devices such as mobile phones and pagers, questioning examination officers that come for visitation unannounced, and prohibiting the use of booklet other than the answer booklet provided for answering of examination questions (Onyibe et al., 2015). Despite several control measures that were put in place to serve as a deterrent to the perpetrators, all are to no avail as examination malpractices are increasing daily. For instance, Examination Malpractice Act 33 of 1999 (revised edition) stipulates that perpetrators should be punished with fines that range from N50,000.00 to N100,000.00 and also imprisonment of perpetrators for 5 years without a fine for the offenses that are stipulated in the Act. This may however be because of non-implementation of the laws (Omeri, 2012).

Statement of problem

Examination malpractices have become a prevalent issue in senior secondary schools in Iwo Local Government area, leading to compromised academic integrity and hindering students' performance. Despite the numerous efforts made by educational authorities to curb the vice, examination malpractices continue to

persist in various forms. The root causes of examination malpractices in senior secondary schools in Iwo Local Government area remain understudied, and there is a lack of comprehensive understanding of the different strategies of malpractices being employed by students. Additionally, effective solutions to combat examination malpractices in these schools have not been adequately explored. Therefore, this research aims to investigate the causes, strategies, and possible solutions to examination malpractices in selected senior secondary schools in Iwo Local Government Area.

Purpose of study

The purpose of studying this research is to identify the causes, strategies, and possible solutions to examination malpractices in selected secondary schools in Iwo Local Government. By conducting this research, we aim to gain a deeper understanding of the factors contributing to examination malpractices, such as student pressure, lack of ethical values, and inadequacies in the examination system.

Furthermore, the study seeks to explore the various strategies of examination malpractices prevalent in the selected schools. The research also aims to propose effective solutions to address examination malpractices in senior secondary schools.

Research question:

The research questions of this study are as follows:

- i. What are the causes of examination malpractices in secondary schools?
- ii. What are the modern strategies used by students to engage in examination malpractice?
- iii. What are the effects of examination malpractice?

- iv. What are the strategies for curbing examination malpractice?

Methodology

This study employed a descriptive survey method to thoroughly describe and evaluate examination malpractices among senior secondary school students: causes, forms and solutions. The research focused on selected senior secondary schools in Iwo Local Government area, Osun State. Due to the impracticality of studying all schools in Iwo Local Government, two schools were purposively selected, one public school and one private school to serve as samples. A total of 100 respondents (50 from each

school), 68 students, and 32 teachers were randomly chosen. Respondents completed a questionnaire titled ‘Examination malpractices’ consisting of two sections: one gathering personal information and the other soliciting responses to structured questions. The questionnaire included 25 questions, with response options categorized as Strongly Agreed (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD).

The researchers personally administered the questionnaires to both teachers and students and gave the respondents adequate time to respond to the questions.

Table 1: The Gender Distribution of the Respondents

S/N	Name of school	GENDER	FREQUENCY
1	LA	Male	34
		Female	16
2	The wings	Male	20
		Female	30
		Total	100

Table 1 above shows the gender distribution of the respondents. Of the 50 respondents at L.A. Commercial Grammar School 34 of them were males while 16 of them were females and at The Wings Group of Schools, we have 20 males and 30 females.

Table 2: The age distribution of the respondents

S/N	Age	Frequency
1	Below 20	60
2	20 -30	18
3	Above 30	22
	Total	100

Table 2 was used to analyze the age distribution of the respondents, those that were below 20 were 60, 18 of them were between the age range of 20 -30 while 22 of them were above 30

Table 3: Marital status of respondents

S/N	Marital status	Frequency
1	Single	70
2	Married	30
	Total	100

Table 3 shows the marital status of the respondents 70 of them were single while the remaining 30 were married.

Table 4: Occupation Status of the Respondents

S/N	Occupation	Frequency
1	Student	68
2	Teacher	32
	Total	100

Table 4 shows the occupation status of the respondents, 68 of them were students while 32 were teachers.

Research Question 1: What are the strategies for examination malpractices?

Table 5: Strategies of examination malpractices

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	SA	A	D	SD	Total
1	Entering examination with foreign materials	28 (28%)	20 (20%)	16 (16%)	24 (24%)	100
2	Assistance from teachers, supervisors and school management.	48 (48%)	26 (26%)	14 (14%)	12 (12%)	100
3	Mass cheating among student	50 (50%)	20 (20%)	12 (12%)	18 (18%)	100
4	Giraffing	20 (20%)	22 (22%)	16 (16%)	22 (22%)	100
5	Impersonation	40 (40%)	26 (26%)	24 (24%)	10 (10%)	100
6	Use of mobile phone	76 (76%)	16 (16%)	6 (6%)	2 (2%)	100
7	Download answers from dubious website	60 (60%)	22 (22%)	8 (8%)	10 (10%)	100
8	Use of iPod to copy notes into examination hall	40 (40%)	36 (36%)	18 (18%)	6 (6%)	100

Table 5 shows forms of examination malpractices about the opinion of respondents on each of the statements. The collation of the questionnaire according to this table shows that the sixth statement has the highest number of respondents (76) that strongly agree with the statement stated while the fourth statement has the least respondents (20) that strongly agree with the statement. The last statement has the highest respondents (36) that agree with it

while the sixth statement has the least respondents (16) that agree with the stated statements. The fifth statement has the highest number of respondents (24) that disagree with the statement while the sixth statement has the least respondents (6) that disagree with it. Most of the respondents (22) strongly disagree with the fourth statement while the least of them (6) strongly disagree with the sixth statement.

Research Question 2: what are the causes of examination malpractices?

Table 6: Causes of examination malpractices

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	SA	A	D	SD	Total
1	The value placed on the educational certificate	50 (50%)	28 (28%)	10 (10%)	12 (12%)	100
2	Inadequate places for candidates seeking admission into Nigerian tertiary institution	40 (40%)	38 (38%)	16 (16%)	6 (6%)	100
3	Parents' desire for their children to acquire certificate	46 (46%)	34 (34%)	10 (10%)	10 (10%)	100
4	Poor teaching method	30 (30%)	20 (20%)	20 (20%)	30 (30%)	100
5	Lack of sound moral behavior	36 (36%)	36 (36%)	18 (18%)	10 (10%)	100
6	Lack of well-equipped library and laboratory	28 (28%)	32 (32%)	22 (22%)	18 (18%)	100

Table 6 shows the result of the statements on the research question on the causes of examination malpractices. It was realized that out of the six statements stated the first statement had the highest number of respondents (50) that strongly agreed with the statement while the last statement had the least respondents (28) that strongly agreed with the stated statement. The second statement has the highest number of respondents (38) who agreed with it while the fourth statement has the least

respondents (20) who agreed with the statement. The last statement had the highest number of respondents (22) that disagreed with the statement while the first and the third statements had the least respondents (10) that disagreed with the statements. The fourth statement had the highest number of respondents (30) out of the six statements that strongly disagreed while the third and fifth statements had the least respondents (10) that strongly disagreed with the statements.

Research Question 3: What are the effects of examination malpractices?

Table 7: Effects of examination malpractices

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	SA	A	D	SD	TOTAL
1	Lack of faith in the effectiveness of educational system	40	40	14	6	100
2	Irresponsibility among students	50	28	18	4	100
3	Increment of student laziness	64	16	10	10	100
4	Inability to defend certificate	70	20	10	0	100
5	Corruption in the educational system	58	30	8	4	100

Table 7 shows the responses of the respondents on the effects of examination malpractices. The fourth statement had the highest number of respondents (70) who strongly agreed with it while the first statement had the least number of respondents (40) who strongly agreed. In the agree column, the first statement had the highest number of respondents (40) while the third statement had the least

respondents (16). The second statement had the highest number of respondents (18) who disagreed with the statement while the last statement had the least respondents (8) who disagreed with it. In the strongly disagree column, the third statement has the highest number of respondents (10) while the fourth statement has the least respondents (0).

Research Question 4: what are the strategies for curbing examination malpractices?

Table 8: solutions of examination malpractices

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	SA	A	D	SD	Total
1	Societal reconstruction and re-orientation of morality	50	44	6	0	100
2	Training and re-training of teachers	58	32	6	4	100
3	Enforcement of the law against examination malpractices	60	24	10	6	100
4	Well-equipped libraries and laboratories	60	30	6	4	100
5	Proper funding of education sectors	52	36	6	6	100
6	Use of continuous assessment appropriately	54	32	4	6	100

Table 8 shows the result of the statements on the research question on strategies for curbing examination malpractices. It was realized that out of the six statements stated, the second and the third statements had the highest number of respondents, (60) that strongly agreed with the statements while the first statement had the least respondents, (50) that strongly agreed with the stated statement. The first statement had the highest number of respondents (44) that agreed with it while the fourth statement had the least number of respondents (30) that agreed with the statement. The third statement had the highest number of respondents (10) that disagreed with the statement while the first, second, fourth, and fifth statements had the least number of respondents (6) that disagreed with the statement. The third, fifth, and sixth statements had the highest number of respondents (6) out of the six statements that strongly disagreed, while the first statement had the least number of respondents (10) that strongly disagreed with the statement.

Discussion of Findings

Examination malpractice is a pressing issue in our education system, necessitating immediate action from stakeholders. This study delves into the prevalent strategies of examination malpractices in senior secondary schools in Iwo Local Government Area, Osun State. It uncovers a range of strategies used, from modern tactics like mobile phone usage and online answer downloads to traditional methods like bringing foreign materials into exams, mass cheating among students, giraffing, impersonation and seeking help from school personnel. The use of mobile phone is the often used strategies of examination by most students according to this study. The causes of examination malpractices varied, with a notable factor being the excessive value placed on

academic certificates. Other contributing factors include limited tertiary institution spaces for students seeking admission, parents' desire for their children on acquiring certificate, poor teaching method, lack of sound moral behavior, and lack of well-equipped library and laboratory. The consequences of examination malpractices are profound, among which are a lack of faith in the effectiveness of the education system, irresponsibility, increment of laziness among students, difficulties in defending qualifications, and corruption in the educational system. The solution to curb the rapid increase in examination malpractices is to strictly enforce the laws, alongside initiatives like the provision of school facilities like libraries and laboratories by the government and school owners, training and re-training of teachers, societal moral rebuilding, sufficient funding for education, and employing continuous assessment methods effectively.

Recommendations

The study recommended the following:

- (i) More value should be placed on what an individual can do than on what certificate he/she might possess. Practical and how well students can implement what they learned should be the basis for evaluation and assessment.
- (ii) Students of secondary schools should not be allowed to be using mobile phones. Parents should curb access to phones by their children at this stage. Also, other school stakeholders should collaborate to achieve success in the misuse of phones by students.
- (iii) Laws on examination malpractices must be enforced,

and culprits brought to book to serve as deterrents to others.

Conclusion

The study concluded that all stakeholders, including students, educators, parents, and educational authorities must acknowledge the dangers inherent in examination malpractices and collaborate to address this issue. The widespread use of mobile phones, the smuggling of materials, and impersonation during exams highlight the urgent need for stricter enforcement of laws. Factors such as an over-emphasis on certificates, limited spaces in tertiary institutions, and ineffective teaching methods must be tackled through improved school facilities, moral development, and ongoing assessments. Safeguarding the future of education requires a united effort and unwavering commitment to ethical principles, academic integrity, and sustainable improvements within the educational system.

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